

D1.4. – First version of MAGIC-CROPS

Due date of deliverable: M12 (30.06.2018)

Actual submission date: M14 (19.09.2018)

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Type

R Document, report

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

DEC Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.

OTHER

Dissemination Level

PU Public

CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 727698.

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1 Executive summary

The MAGIC-CROPS database is an easy-to-use tool describing 37 promising species suited to marginal land as defined in the JRC's report (EUR 23412 EN - 2008 and later modifications). Crop descriptions include general botanical and morphological characteristics, agricultural practices, potential yield and quality, and current and potential uses. An evaluation score (0 to 3, unfeasible, high, moderate and low decrease of potential yield caused by biophysical constrains) is used to describe crop suitability to develop under different marginal conditions. The MAGIC-CROPS database will be continuously updated throughout the project. The present deliverable is an early version of the database including switchgrass, camelina, sugar beet, willow, lupin, wild sugarcane, giant reed, Siberian elm, Spanish broom, tall wheatgrass, cardoon, lavender.

2 Introduction

During the two first technical meetings the consortium agreed on the outline of MAGIC-CROPS database into four main sections: general description, crop suitability for different biophysical constraints, cultivation practices, and qualitative traits according to current and potential uses.

The participants in charge to different crops. Table 1 shows the lead partners in charge to fill different crops of the database.

Table 1: Lead partners in charge to provide species' description.

Species	Partner in charge to fill MAGIC-CROPS database
Switchgrass	UNIBO
Camelina	UNIBO
Sorghum	CRES
Crambe	WUR
Castorbean	CRES
Miscanthus	UHOH
Giant reed	UNICT
Tall wheatgrass	CIEMAT
Amaranth	UHOH
Sunflower	UNICT
Etiopian mustrad	UNIBO
Hemp	UNICT
Flax	IWNiRZ
Reed canary grass	LSFRI SILAVA
Common reed	UNIBO
Spanish broom	CIEMAT
Safflower	CRES
Nettle	IWNiRZ
Cardoon	UNICT
Guayule	WUR
Pennycress	UNIBO
Willow	IBCSB NAASU
Poplar	LSFRI SILAVA
Black locust	CRES
Eucalyptus	UNL-FCT
Siberian elm	CIEMAT
Wild sugarcane	UNICT
Lupin	WUR
Wild tobacco (tree)	CRES
Saltbush	CRES

Jerusalem artichoke	UNIBO
Kenaf	CRES
Sunn hemp	UNIBO
Caper spurge / euphorbia	UNIBO
Sugar beets	IBCSB NAASU
Calendula	WUR
True lavender	INRA

3 Early version of MAGIC-CROPS Database

See annexed excel file